

Notas breves

Observations on the uncommon predation of an endangered limpet, *Patella ferruginea*, by an *Octopus vulgaris* in the Chafarinas Islands

Observaciones de una predación poco común sobre una especie de lapa en peligro, *Patella ferruginea*, por *Octopus vulgaris* en las islas Chafarinas

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The ferruginous limpet *Patella ferruginea* (Gmelin, 1791) is an endemic species of the western Mediterranean, where it is considered one of the most threatened invertebrate species (TEMPLADO, CALVO, GARVÍA, LUQUE, MALDONADO ET AL., 2004; LUQUE, GUALLART, TEMPLADO & POLA, 2018). The regression of the species has been attributed to human harvesting (for consumption, bait or, more recently, shell collection), habitat degradation, coastal modifications by infrastructures and pollution (LABOREL-DEGUEN & LABOREL, 1991a; TEMPLADO ET AL., 2004).

Patella ferruginea has some natural predators, whose effects have not yet been analysed in detail. The marine gastropod *Stramonita haemastoma* (Linnaeus, 1767) is probably its main predator

(TEMPLADO ET AL., 2004; GUALLART, 2006; 2008; GUALLART & ACEVEDO, 2006; GONZÁLEZ-GARCÍA, PAREDES RUIZ, ENRIQUE MIRÓN, CALZADO LIARTE & BUENO DEL CAMPO, 2015; ZARROUK, ROMDHANE & ESPINOSA, 2018). This species changes its feeding behavior depending on the size of its prey: for small limpets, it lifts and preys along the edge of the shell, but for medium- to large-sized limpets, it drills into the shell, which may take up to 2 to 3 days of activity (GUALLART & ACEVEDO, 2006; GUALLART, 2008). Other species have been described as predators of *P. ferruginea* including the decapod crustacean *Eriphia verrucosa* (Forskål, 1775) (LABOREL-DEGUEN & LABOREL, 1991b; GUALLART & ACEVEDO, 2006); predation by this crustacean is thought to only

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occur while *P. ferruginea* specimens are moving for feeding purposes (GUALLART, 2008). Other crabs such as *Pachygrapsus marmoratus* (Fabricius, 1787) (ESPINOSA, GONZÁLEZ-ARANDA, MAESTRE-DELGADO, FA, GUERRA-GARCÍA & GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, 2007; COPPA, DE LUCIA, MASSARO & MAGNI, 2012) and *Carcinus mediterraneus* Czerniavsky, 1884 (COPPA ET AL., 2012) have also been cited as predators of *P. ferruginea*. Likewise, gulls have been indicated as predators of the species, although through indirect information: LABOREL-DEGUEN & LABOREL (1991b) cited a personal observation of M. Thibault and GUALLART (2006; 2008) suggested possible predation by the yellow-legged gull *Larus michahellis* Naumann, 1840 from an observation of recent empty shells in areas almost inaccessible to humans and where this gull species is often found. An anecdotal case of predation by the infralittoral gastropod *Hexaplex trunculus* (Linnaeus, 1758) has also been reported (DONEDDU, 2015).

The Chafarinas Islands (35°11'N 02°26'W) are one of the few localities where an important population of *P. ferruginea* can still be found (GUALLART & TEMPLADO, 2016), which has allowed numerous studies to be carried out

about its biology (see LUQUE ET AL., 2018). On May 26, 2012, an adult *P. ferruginea* specimen was observed on an isolated rock located approximately 60 m from the western coast of Isabel II of the Chafarinas Islands. The specimen had a shell length greater than 80 mm and, therefore, was undoubtedly an adult (FRENKIEL, 1975; ESPINOSA, GUERRA-GARCÍA, FA, & GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, 2006; GUALLART, CALVO, ACEVEDO & TEMPLADO, 2013). Notably, it was observed in a habitat where the species is not usually found. *Patella ferruginea* inhabits the upper midlittoral fringe (LUQUE ET AL., 2018), above the mean sea level. In the Chafarinas Islands, a range of lunisolar tides exists, although it is very limited (usually between 10 and 25 cm; pers. obs.). The specimen was located in the infralittoral zone, at a depth of approximately -0.8 m, well below the area's tidal range (Figure 1A) and below the narrow strip of corallinaceae which represents the lower midlittoral fringe and usually limits movements of *P. ferruginea* towards the lower levels (GUALLART, 2006). The rock on which it was found was partially covered by macroalgae, but the limpet was settled on a surface that can be considered as a "blanquizal" (Figure 1B, C),

(Right page) Figure 1. A: schematic showing the common habitat of *Patella ferruginea* specimens (blue ovals) on the upper midlittoral fringe and the location of the studied specimen (red oval) in the infralittoral zone on a rock isolated from the coast. The continuous horizontal line represents the mean sea level and the dashed lines represent the upper and lower limits of the tidal range in the Chafarinas Islands. The corallinaceae algae typical of the lower midlittoral zone is represented in grey. Scale on the left is in meters. B, C: *P. ferruginea* specimen observed on May 26, 2012. D-F: *P. ferruginea* specimen being attacked by an *Octopus vulgaris*. G: *P. ferruginea* shell recovered on May 28, 2012, showing some details of a perforation similar to that commonly made by *S. haemastoma* (see text); scale represents 20 mm in the general figure and 40 mm in the insets.

(Página derecha) Figura 1. A: esquema mostrando el hábitat habitual de *Patella ferruginea* (óvalos azules) en el piso mediolitoral superior y la localización del ejemplar estudiado (óvalo rojo) en la zona infralitoral en una roca aislada de la costa. La línea horizontal continua representa el nivel medio del mar y las líneas discontinuas representan los límites superior e inferior del rango de mareas en las islas Chafarinas. En gris se representa la franja de algas coralináceas típica del piso mediolitoral inferior. La escala de izquierda es en metros. B, C: ejemplar de *P. ferruginea* observado el 26 de mayo de 2012. D-F: ejemplar de *P. ferruginea* siendo atacado por un *Octopus vulgaris*. G: concha de *P. ferruginea* recuperada el 28 de mayo de 2012, mostrando detalles de una perforación similar a la hecha habitualmente por *S. haemastoma* (ver texto); la escala representa 20 mm en la figura general y 40 mm en los cuadros de detalle.

an area free of macroalgae due to intensive browsing by the sea urchins *Paracentrotus lividus* (Lamarck, 1816) and *Arbacia lixula* (Linnaeus, 1758).

The reason for its unusual location, far from its usual habitat, was not initially clear. We hypothesized that the specimen fell from its midlittoral habitat and managed to take a grip on the rock. Unlike other gastropods, when limpets detach from the substrate, they are completely vulnerable to predation by many groups (e.g., crabs, octopuses and fishes), as they cannot retract their soft body parts into the shell. It is highly unlikely that the specimen would have reached this depth otherwise, given the species' habitat limitations described above (GUALLART, 2006).

One day later (May 27, 2012), a common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris* Cuvier, 1797) was observed near the limpet (Figure 1D) and, soon after, on it (Figure 1E, F). Several hours later, the *P. ferruginea* specimen had disappeared. After an exhaustive search of the nearby grounds, a fresh empty *P. ferruginea* shell was found. Comparison of the shell with the photographs taken of the specimen the previous day, taking into account details such as the presence and location of some *Chthamalus* spp., confirmed that the shell belongs to that specimen. The shell, which was 85.0 mm in length, presented a small perforation (Figure 1G), somewhat resembling the characteristic shape of those made by drilling *S. haemastoma*: somewhat broader outside and narrower inside, giving it a sub-conical shape (LUQUE ET AL., 2018). However, in the case of that *P. ferruginea* shell, the inner diameter of the opening (about 0.55 mm) seemed comparatively smaller than that observed in other shells drilled by *S. haemastoma* (pers. obs.). The shell has been deposited in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid, Spain) with the catalog number MNCN 15.05/46990.

Our hypothesis is that a *S. haemastoma* attempted to prey on the *P. ferru-*

ginea specimen and managed to drill into the shell. However, before the snail could kill the limpet, the latter fell about 1 m of depth, where it was able to attach to the rock and survive but unable to return to its midlittoral habitat. Then, in its new location, a common octopus, which has markedly infralittoral habits, had the opportunity to prey on it.

We consider these observations to be somewhat unusual: (1) the presence of *P. ferruginea* in a markedly infralittoral zone, a habitat in which the species has not been recorded in the Chafarinas Islands, despite numerous years of study; (2) the presence of a perforation in the limpet's shell attributable to *S. haemastoma* but which did not cause its death, given that, on the first day of observation, the specimen was firmly attached to the rock; and (3) we suggest the fact that the common octopus must not be considered a usual predator of *P. ferruginea*. Therefore, this case represents an anomalous or anecdotal event. Regardless, records of these types of observations contribute to the knowledge of *P. ferruginea* habitats and predators, information that is essential for its management and the actions aimed at its conservation.

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